

1 **Was the Late Glacial human occupation of northernmost**
2 **Europe facilitated by whales? New data and perspectives on**
3 **lithic technology and the palaeoecology of the Vendsyssel area,**
4 **Northern Jutland, Denmark**

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11 **Abstract**

12 *The archaeology of the Vendsyssel area in Northern Jutland suggests that early*
13 *human foragers reached the northernmost tip of continental Europe during the*
14 *middle part of the Late Glacial. This occupation presents a palaeoecological*
15 *conundrum, however, as Vendsyssel was likely characterised by low terrestrial*
16 *productivity and mammalian biodiversity. Why did human foragers disperse so far*
17 *north, and what sustained them there? We here report an updated inventory of*
18 *Late Glacial lithic surface material recovered from the Hollendskær region in*
19 *north-western Jutland. Based on our discussion of the lithic assemblages, we*
20 *recontextualise human settlement in the European far north vis-à-vis highly*
21 *productive marine ecosystems in the circum-Kattegat. We suggest that beached*
22 *whales may have been a previously overlooked ecological attractor as persistent*
23 *terrestrial biases impede our understanding of the role of land-sea interfaces in*
24 *facilitating the earliest northward human expansions.*

25 **Keywords:** Final Palaeolithic; cetaceans; human-sea relations; tanged points;
26 blue humanities

27

28 **Introduction**

29 The Allerød warm period (ca. 14,000-12,800 years ago) in Southern Scandinavia is
30 characterised by the development of lacustrine, estuary and riverine birch or birch-pine
31 woodland landscapes in eastern Denmark, northern Germany and southern Sweden,
32 whereas open heathland environments typified the northern and western parts of the
33 Jutland peninsula (Bennike, Sarmaja-Korjonen, and Seppänen 2004; Mortensen,
34 Henriksen, and Bennike 2014). This ecological division between the northwest and the
35 east became especially pronounced in the second half of the Allerød (Mortensen,
36 Henriksen, and Bennike 2014), when the archaeological record of the wider region is
37 marked by the co-occurrence of lithic assemblages with arched-backed bladelets
38 (Federmesser) and large ‘tanged’ or ‘stemmed’ points with substantial morpho-
39 typometric variability (Fischer 1991; Price 2015, 34; Riede 2013; 2017). In Denmark,
40 both Federmesser (FMG) and especially tanged-point (Brommean) assemblages are
41 mainly distributed across the eastern lake-woodland complex (Becker 1971; Fischer
42 1991) with its system of fjords, inlets and small islands, providing easy access to the
43 Yoldia Sea – the incipient Kattegat. This is not to say that these sites are coastal – many
44 larger sites are found inland – but that oceanic connectivity played perhaps a more
45 significant role in Late Glacial land-use systems than often assumed. The recent discovery
46 of strictly coastal Allerød sites of potential FMG-affiliation in western Sweden adds to
47 this emerging picture (Nordqvist 2017).

48 Interestingly, the Vendsyssel peninsula has produced a dense cluster of
49 archaeological sites probably dating to the Allerød (Nilsson 1987; Fischer 1991; 2012;
50 Nilsson, Kristensen, and Frandsen 1988; **Fig. 1**), all located outside of the main focus
51 areas of Late Glacial human activity in Denmark (Lundström, Peters, and Riede 2021),
52 and well beyond the birch-line. The large majority of Danish Allerød sites dates to the

53 later stage of the Allerød and is found in the east, where birch woodland prevailed, thus
54 rendering the Vendsyssel sites a notable anomaly. What was the motivation for people to
55 travel so far north? Did the dynamic island landscape afford unique foraging opportunities and
56 hunter-gatherer lifeways not viable further south?

57 This paper presents new Final Palaeolithic surface assemblages recovered from
58 the Hollendskær region in the north-western part of Vendsyssel, and places them in their
59 archaeological and palaeoecological context. We reignite discussion on the role of tanged
60 points and tanged (Wehlen-type) scrapers within adaptations that incipiently include
61 coastal resources. During the Allerød period, human foragers reached northwards, pulled
62 in by the retreating glaciers, by dispersing animal species, and by the novel productive
63 environments of Late Glacial Southern Scandinavia. We argue that their distinctive lithic
64 tools were flexible and versatile components of high-mobility adaptive systems, which
65 took advantage of the seasonal availability of high-value oceanic resources such as
66 beached whales in the area. We suggest that at first sight marginal landscapes at the newly
67 formed eastern extension of the North Atlantic seaboard thus afforded unique contexts of
68 experimentation with land-sea interfaces at the end of the Pleistocene. These
69 considerations lead us to the proposal that cetaceans may have been a key ecological
70 attractor for people in high-latitude Late Glacial Europe, nourishing northern forager
71 lifeways, facilitating landscape learning, and framing human-nonhuman cohabitation.

72 **Lithic assemblages from Hollendskær, north-western Denmark**

73 Hollendskær in north-western Jutland is long known for its Late Glacial surface
74 archaeology (Nilsson 1987; Nilsson, Kristensen, and Frandsen 1988; Fischer 1991;
75 Hellerøe et al. 2023) and has recently received new attention as ‘an island at the end of
76 the world’ (Fischer 2012). The first sites were discovered there in 1983 in the context of

77 amateur surveys conducted by Finn G. Frandsen and Otto Emil Kristensen in
78 collaboration with the Vendsyssel Historical Museum (VHM). The two key site
79 complexes of Ramsgård and Varbro are located close to Bjergby, about 7 km north of
80 Hjørring on the northern tip of the Jutland peninsula. Archaeological test excavations
81 were carried out by the VHM at the sites of Ramsgård I and II in 1987 (VHM file no.
82 285-286/1986) but no preserved archaeological layers were found, and new test trenching
83 in 2022 by VHM and the Department of Archaeology and Heritage Studies from Aarhus
84 University at the site of Kærgård Nord unfortunately also failed to identify any preserved
85 find horizons. The prevalence of large tanged points in conjunction with larger
86 endscrapers and burins at the Ramsgård and Varbro sites (**Fig. 2**) prompted Nilsson
87 (1989) to assign the lithic material to the Bromme complex. The stone artefact
88 assemblages were then set in a wider climatic and cultural context foregrounding
89 terrestrial big-game hunting and logistical settlement patterns (Nilsson, Kristensen and
90 Frandsen 1988), based on the assumption that Vendsyssel in the Late Glacial was part of
91 the larger Southern Scandinavian land area.

92 The Vendsyssel sites including Højvælde, Trudslev and the Hollendskær cluster
93 are all located in former wetland areas and on elevated positions on moraine or Yoldia
94 sea deposits in close proximity to the former coast (Nilsson 1987; Nilsson, Kristensen,
95 and Frandsen 1988), similar to the most intensely investigated palaeolake at Nørre Lyngy
96 (Fischer, Clemmensen, et al. 2013). Hollendskær probably harboured a shallow Late
97 Glacial freshwater lake covering an area of about 0.5 km² and the Ramsgård and Varbro
98 sites therefore recapitulate some of the locational parameters already noted for other
99 Bromme sites in Jutland (Fischer 1991; Fischer, Clemmensen, et al. 2013). Many of these
100 sites are situated close to important inland water bodies, which in turn facilitate direct
101 access to coastal landscapes and catchments, and the sites therefore often demarcate

102 strategic ecotonal positions. Despite the presence of wetland lakes acting as vital
103 biodiversity hotspots, northernmost Jutland is often pictured as a somewhat barren, low-
104 productivity landscape (cf. Hellerøe et al. 2023) – as an open park-tundra with low-
105 growing vegetation including dwarf shrubs, heather and willow and reduced mammalian
106 diversity (e.g., Mortensen, Henriksen, and Bennike 2014; Fischer et al. 2013; Iversen
107 1942). Notably, faunal evidence for the purported main prey species of Bromme foragers
108 such as elk and giant deer is currently lacking from the region. In addition, and in Jutland
109 particularly, large tanged points of supposedly ‘Brommean’ affiliation are regularly
110 recovered as stray finds (cf. **Fig. 3**) and the Hollendskær area is no exception: larger
111 concentrations of stone artefacts are interspersed with isolated finds, often points.

112 Nilsson (1989) originally reported 15 larger artefact concentrations from
113 Hollendskær to which he referred to as ‘settlements’, as well as 12 single finds, 10 of
114 which were described as tanged points. An overview of these original find contexts is
115 given in **Table 1**. Since then, new lithic find locations have been discovered and
116 documented by the VHM, most notably Varbro V south of the original Ramsgård
117 complex and the Kærgård sites in the east, immediately neighbouring the town of
118 Bjergby. In addition, new surface material has been collected from the original sites
119 identified by Nilsson (1989: Ramsgård I, II, IV, V, VI, VII and IX) and a new assemblage
120 was added – Nørre Ramsgård. **Figure 4** shows the location and distribution of these old
121 and newer sites in the Hollendskær area. While small, these sites together attest to a
122 landscape of repeated human activity rather than a single occupational event. The added
123 lithic material recovered from the area is described here in detail for the first time,
124 providing the opportunity to update our understanding of Final Palaeolithic life in Late
125 Glacial Vendsyssel.

126 **Updating the record: the new Final Palaeolithic find complexes**

127 *Overview and general characteristics of the assemblages*

128 The Hollendskær area comprises three site clusters: the Ramsgård sites at the western
129 banks and promontory of the former Late Glacial lake, the Varbro complex at the southern
130 banks, and the two Kærgård sites slightly further up on the eastern promontory. The
131 Ramsgård complex has been extended further north, adding Nørre Ramsgård as a new
132 find concentration, while Ramsgård I, II, IV, V, VI, VII and IX have yielded additional
133 lithic artefacts. Varbro V has been added to the Varbro site complex at the eastern
134 extension of the former lake banks in the south, and Kærgård Nord and Syd were newly
135 discovered. A detailed breakdown of the composition of these lithic find contexts is
136 provided in **Table 2**.

137 The new material from the Hollendskær area reported here encompasses 494 lithic
138 artefacts in total. The majority of the material consists of unretouched débitage (n=367;
139 74%), followed by 118 tools (24%) and only a small number of cores (n=7; 1%).
140 Fragments are not very frequent (n=35), likely as a consequence of sampling bias, and
141 were included in the débitage counts. Due to the same bias, tools are overrepresented (cf.
142 Riede 2017). Among these, Upper and Final Palaeolithic tool types clearly dominate:
143 tanged points form the largest group (n=31), followed by endscrapers (n=22), burins
144 (n=9), borers (n=6) and notched pieces (n=5), often on blades. Among the scrapers, ten
145 artefacts have tangs and can be classified as so-called ‘Wehlen’ scrapers (cf.
146 Schwabedissen 1954), although their morpho-typological characteristics vary.
147 Truncations are rare (n=2). Notably, a single broken arch-backed point (Federmesser)
148 was recovered from Ramsgård II. Another important group are informal tools, including
149 partially and laterally retouched pieces (n=33). This also includes knife-like forms which
150 have already been highlighted by Nilsson (1989) as an important component of the

151 original Hollendskær assemblages. Reminiscent artefacts from Rekem have been
152 described as large ‘laterally modified pieces’ (≥ 12 mm width) by Casper and De Bie
153 (1996) or as *lames à retouche rasante* (e.g., Roberts and Barton 2021), which is consistent
154 with a Final Palaeolithic placement of such finds. In addition, various non-typical blade
155 points (n=3) and laterally retouched bladelets (n=4) occur at the Hollendskær sites. Some
156 of these informal tools may reflect the utilisation of initially unretouched blanks rather
157 than representing prior-to-use modified pieces and thus lithic ‘tools’ in the conventional
158 sense of the term. This possible role of selected, unretouched blanks for basic cutting-
159 edge supply is a known and often underrated feature in the techno-economic profile of
160 some Final Palaeolithic technologies.

161 Unretouched bladelets are moderately frequent in the new material (n=44), while
162 flakes (n=142) and blades (n=134) are equally important. It is likely that sampling bias
163 has favoured blades in this regard. Bladelets are mainly defined metrically (max.
164 width=12 mm), and the respective products are thus not necessarily very regular. Well-
165 defined preparatory products (core trimming elements: CTEs) are rare (n=9). Together
166 with cortical surfaces being documented on 36% of all artefacts, this suggests that blank
167 production was not preceded by extensive core configuration procedures and/or that lithic
168 material was already introduced in a preconfigured manner or as blanks/tools. This is
169 consistent with only a handful of cores encountered in the Hollendskær material,
170 especially given that many of these objects bear only a small number of removals and
171 thus often represent tested pieces.

172

173 ***Tanged points, Wehlen scrapers and tool reduction dynamics: some initial observations***

174 Tanged points and scrapers are a key component of the lithic toolkits recovered from the
175 Hollendskær landscape (**Fig. 5, 6**). The new material has yielded 31 tanged points and 10

176 tanged Wehlen-type scrapers, while Nilsson et al. (1988) reported 33 tanged points and 7
177 tanged scrapers (n=64/17) (see also Nilsson 1987). The number of published tanged
178 elements from Hollendskær has therefore almost been doubled (n=81). In the material
179 reported here, only 10 points are complete, and 21 pieces are broken medially, or they
180 bear distal impact scars. Both tanged points and Wehlen scrapers are extremely variable
181 in their shape and dimensions. The Hollendskær points – very likely also overrepresented
182 due recovery and sampling biases (cf. Riede 2017) – mostly conform to the metric
183 definition of large tanged Brommean points (width>15 mm), although some specimens
184 are smaller.

185 Inspired by Schmitt’s (1999) classic suggestion to reconsider flint axes found in
186 incipient Holocene Hensbacka contexts on the west coast of Sweden in analogy to so-
187 called ‘Ulu’ tools used by Indigenous people in the circumarctic to work skin and blubber
188 of marine mammals, Hellererøe and colleagues (2023) have proposed a similar role for
189 some of tanged scrapers found at Hollendskær. At first sight, however, the substantial
190 morpho-technical variability embodied by Wehlen-type and other tanged scraper forms
191 appears inconsistent with such a well-defined tool function. This being said, it is
192 important to not regard them as ‘final’ or ‘desired’ forms but rather as residuals within a
193 larger landscape of discard, and as such potentially as nodes in a transformation
194 continuum.

195 A single, somewhat atypical tanged scraper from Hollendskær (cf. **Fig. 5.7**)
196 provides direct and otherwise difficult-to-come-by evidence for such a larger reduction
197 continuum. Interestingly, the scraper modification is not fully installed on the distal
198 ventral side of the artefact and has thus not been completed. The piece showcases the
199 attempt to rework a precursor tool with already pre-established tang, most likely a broken
200 tanged point or an even larger scraper, and to re-establish or re-furbish its functionality.

201 Such ongoing rejuvenation is also attested for other tanged elements. Nilsson (1987: Fig.
202 19.2) for example depicts a tanged point which was apparently reworked into a dihedral
203 burin (cf. **Fig. 2.17**). Mathiassen (1946: Fig. 6.10 and 16.11) shows similar examples
204 from the eponymous site of Bromme. Some larger tanged elements, for example the
205 artefact shown in **Figure 2.13** were, furthermore, either never designed to sport a
206 convergent distal end or they were later reworked to serve different functions (here as a
207 possible truncation). Other so-called tanged points exhibit tips that are created by
208 notching and are thus formally more reminiscent of borers/perforators than alleged
209 projectile tips (cf. **Fig. 2.5**). The mere configuration of distal ends of tanged artefacts in
210 the Vendsyssel material is bewilderingly heterogeneous and this diversity defies simple
211 functional unity. At Trollesgave in Zealand, Donahue and Fischer (2015) have shown that
212 Brommean tanged point indeed bear varied use-wear patterns and were thus probably
213 deployed in a range of different functional and techno-economic contexts.

214 The diversity of distal configurations of larger tanged artefacts alone – from U-
215 shaped to V-shaped of various angularities – thus probably signals functional versatility
216 and the need to employ and re-use transported objects flexibly. From a techno-functional
217 perspective, tanged points with a cortical surface opposing a single sharp cutting edge are
218 for example more appropriately addressed as ‘knives’ than points (cf. **Fig. 2.4**). It is
219 therefore possible, but cannot demonstrated conclusively, that at least some of the tanged
220 scrapers, especially the smaller specimens, represent later stages in a larger, potentially
221 integrated transformation chain of tanged pieces. At the very least, it has to be said that
222 tanged points, knives and scrapers likely existed, and they were part of the same mobile
223 forager toolkit, with somewhat fluid boundaries between them. The large size of the initial
224 blanks on which many of them were manufactured is relevant in this context, as such
225 blanks provide ample future reworking potential and thus serve as mobile lithic raw

226 material reservoirs. An instructive analogy may be provided by the French tanged
227 Gravettian points, where tanged knives, points and scrapers similarly coexist and in which
228 many of the pieces formerly interpreted as projectiles have now been shown to represent
229 flexible knives (Taipale and Rots 2021).

230

231 **Revisiting the palaeogeography and changing sea-levels of the Vendsyssel area**

232 To place the updated lithic record from Hollendskær into its archaeological and ecological
233 context and discuss its possible broader relevance, we here revisit the palaeogeography
234 of the Vendsyssel area, including general dynamics of past sea-level change. Due to
235 severe isostatic depression caused by the ice sheets formed during the preceding
236 Weichselian Ice Age, the Vendsyssel area was initially transgressed by the Yoldia Sea
237 during the Oldest Dryas (approx.. 18-15,000 years ago). At the height of this transgression
238 at the transition to the Late Glacial period, the relative sea level (RSL) was more than 60
239 m above the present day mean sea level (MSL) in the northernmost part of Vendsyssel
240 (Mertz 1924). The Yoldia transgression deposited marine clay and sands, forming the so-
241 called ‘Vendsyssel Formation’ (Krohn et al. 2009). The upper part of this formation
242 comprises the distinct Zirfaea Beds (Jessen 1936). In contrast to the typical Yoldia clay
243 deposits, these beds are characterized by the incorporation of arctic-boreal fauna and are
244 described as a transgression-regression facies (Jessen 1936; Aaris-Sørensen and Petersen
245 1984). The Zirfaea Sea transgression has been correlated to Bølling period (Krog and
246 Tauber 1974a) where melt water pulse 1A (MWP-1A) culminated in the early Allerød
247 period, approx. 13,800 years ago (Krog and Tauber 1974a). Due to continued isostatic
248 lift, the Zirfaea Sea subsequently regresses throughout the Allerød period, affording
249 human and animal incursions and sustained biotic exchange with the continent.

250 This regression is followed by a pronounced mainland period associated with the
251 Younger Dryas, followed once again by a transgression of the boreal Littorina Sea in the
252 subsequent early Holocene. The Littorina transgression has eroded and buried the
253 majority of the Zirfaea coastline and Zirfaea beds have only been identified in the
254 northern parts of Vendsyssel. The beds in this region are located there more than 16 m
255 above the present-day MSL, though Jessen (1936) argues that the transgression may have
256 reached 20 m above MSL (**Fig. 7**). The regional preservation of the Zirfaea coast
257 attributed to the northward gradient of the isostatic rebound. The RSL of the Zirfaea Sea
258 in in the Aalborg area, south of Vendsyssel, would have been similar to, or even below
259 the modern MSL (**Fig. 8**). Consequently, besides Norway and Sweden, Vendsyssel is the
260 only place where the Bølling-Allerød coast is preserved and exposed, and the only
261 location with a direct connection to the continent. It is important to stress that the isostatic
262 lift and resulting transgression-regression pattern are complex and not fully understood.
263 The isostatic curve and resulting RSL shown in **Figure 8** are a simplified representation
264 intended to provide general understanding of the pattern.

265 Overall the current picture suggests that Late Glacial Vendsyssel was not truly an
266 island in the strictest sense of the term. The basemap shown in **Figure 1** in fact depicts
267 the conditions during the peak of the Yoldia transgression, several millennia before the
268 suspected timing of Final Palaeolithic human presence in Northern Jutland. Another
269 noteworthy characteristic of northern Late Glacial Vendsyssel is the gradual decrease in
270 relative sea level (RSL) during the Allerød period, while isostatic lift remains robust and
271 eustatic sea level (ESL) is stagnant (cf. **Fig. 8**), indicating a relative unstable coastal
272 environment.

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274

275 **Cetaceans as ecological landscape attractors?**

276 The updated evidence from Vendsyssel, now also comprising the fragment of a
277 Federmesser-like backed implement supporting a broadly Allerød chronology of the lithic
278 material from the area, provides a new opportunity to reconsider the ecological and
279 adaptive context of early human excursions into the far North. Published radiocarbon-
280 dated faunal remains from Northern Jutland yielding Late Glacial ages suggest that
281 mammal communities were impoverished and especially carnivores were relatively rare.
282 The terrestrial animal record is mainly characterised by reindeer that were seasonally
283 present in the opening heather-parkland corridor connecting Jutland with Western and
284 Central Europe (see e.g. Mortensen et al. 2014). The only documented predators are polar
285 bears and these animals are known to have evolved anti-starvation metabolism enabling
286 them to survive many months without feeding if necessary (Laidre et al. 2018). Reduced
287 terrestrial biomass availability is also signalled by the pollen evidence from the area
288 (Mortensen, Henriksen, and Bennike 2014; Fischer et al. 2013; Iversen 1942), which has
289 sparked imaginations of northernmost Late Glacial Denmark as a barren, circumpolar
290 shrub-bearing steppe of questionable attraction. From this palaeoecological perspective,
291 the well-documented Late Glacial archaeology of the Vendsyssel area represents a
292 conundrum as foragers would be expected to avoid the area and concentrate their
293 activities on other parts of north-western Europe. Is it therefore possible that current
294 debates overlook important ecosystem dynamics that may have attracted or at least
295 sustained human foragers in these northern extremes?

296 We suggest that the resolution of the Vendsyssel conundrum is currently impeded
297 by an overriding terrestrial bias assuming that early human foraging systems in Northern
298 Jutland are primarily to be understood as land-based adaptations. This implicit
299 terrestrocentrism is anchored in broader narratives of the recolonisation of higher latitude

300 Europe during the Late Glacial in which terrestrial ungulates are stipulated as the most
301 significant ecological pull factors, sometimes in conjunction with putative population
302 pressure in forager core areas further south (Fuglestedt 2012). While the latter is difficult
303 to support by coupled palaeoecological and palaeodemographic modelling (Yaworsky,
304 Hussain, and Riede 2023), the former may provide a partial answer at best given the
305 above-outlined ecological context of northern Jutland.

306 Another key source of the prevailing land bias is the discursive construction of
307 Bromme itself, as this phenomenon is traditionally depicted as a foraging system
308 anchored in large terrestrial prey animals such as reindeer, giant deer and elk (Price 2015;
309 J. G. D. Clark 1938; Jensen 2013). and this is well-reflected in earlier interpretations of
310 the lithic material from the Hollendskær area (Nilsson, Kristensen, and Frandsen 1988).
311 However, remains of these large terrestrial prey are mostly confined to eastern Denmark
312 and northern Germany (Bratlund 1996; Wild, Fischer Mortensen, et al. 2022) where
313 ecological conditions were markedly different during the Late Glacial. As Fischer and
314 colleagues (2013) have recently pointed out, the time is thus ripe to critically reconsider
315 the role of land-water interfaces in Late Glacial northern forager adaptations.

316 With regard to the arctic ocean taking shape during the Late Glacial in Southern
317 Scandinavia as the glaciers progressively recede, coastal productivity is an often-
318 underrated ecological factor for forager settlement. This is especially so when
319 sophisticated boat and marine extraction technologies are unavailable as was likely the
320 case in the Final Palaeolithic of Northern Europe (Glørstad 2013; Wild, Jensen, et al.
321 2022). Palaeogeographic and sea-level reconstructions of Late Glacial northern Jutland,
322 when linked to the often-volatile climatic transformations of the time period, generally
323 suggest a highly dynamic land-sea interface, with rapidly progressing and receding ocean
324 fronts. This dynamic promotes specific ecological and landform successions and the

325 formation of heterogeneous ecotonal coastal landforms including lagoons and wetlands
326 with high biodiversity potential, even if these are comparatively unstable. Wren and
327 colleagues (2020) have shown that rapid shoreline displacement can be a potent attractor
328 for human occupation and can strongly modulate site choice as well as mobility. They
329 propose that a trade-off between site stability and resource diversity underwritten by
330 coastal dynamics governs much of human spatial decision-making in such contexts,
331 making coastal dynamics themselves a key locational factor. Archaeological sites in
332 Jutland attributed to the Allerød are often found on stable elevations yet close to shoreline
333 deposits, raising the possibility that a similar rationale also structured human landscape
334 use in Bromme and perhaps the Allerød more generally.

335 The second dimension of coastal productivity to highlight here is the input of
336 marine biomass to terrestrial systems. Laidre and colleagues (2018), for example, have
337 shown that marine subsidised terrestrial food webs can play critical roles in facilitating
338 predators where primary productivity is otherwise low. In the circumpolar Arctic, polar
339 bears can sustain themselves by scavenging on dead floating and/or beached large whales,
340 when the sea ice retreats and seals as well as other favoured prey species are not readily
341 available. Laidre et al. (2018) calculate that such cetacean-sponsored resources,
342 especially of large baleen whales such as bowheads and grey whales, provide a
343 statistically reliable high-value food source for polar bears who often congregate in the
344 hundreds at the stranding sites. These calculations are based on estimated present-day
345 population sizes of these whales, which are likely to have been higher in the past, when
346 glacial melting delivered highly productive marine waters to Southern Scandinavia, and
347 before whale stocks were depleted due to industrial hunting.

348 Cetacean remains from the circum-Kattegat area are remarkably abundant and
349 specimens dated to the Late Glacial in particular rival their Holocene counterparts in

350 quantity (Aaris-Sørensen et al. 2010), and this is in spite of the record being possibly
351 strongly biased in favour of Holocene whales. The Late Glacial whale record is dominated
352 by bowhead (*B. mysticetus*) and beluga (*D. leucas*) as well as North Atlantic right whale
353 (*E. glacialis*) and some humpbacks (*M. novaeangliae*), taking into consideration the
354 currently available cetacean evidence from Denmark (Aaris-Sørensen et al. 2010),
355 southwestern Sweden (Fredèn 1975) and southern Norway (Wiig, Bachmann, and
356 Hufthammer 2019). Analyses of south-western Norwegian bowhead aDNA have recently
357 confirmed that bowhead populations were surprisingly large and well-established in the
358 eastern North Atlantic during the Late Glacial (Wiig, Bachmann, and Hufthammer 2019;
359 Foote et al. 2013).

360 Notable is also the current lack of killer whales (*O. orca*) in the Late Pleistocene
361 record of the region, which together with the rarity of presently dated seal remains from
362 the Late Glacial of northern Jutland poses interesting questions as to the nature and
363 functioning of these early oceanic ecosystems. Killer whales are apex marine predators
364 and often prey upon both seals and whales, including larger whales (de Bruyn, Tosh, and
365 Terauds 2013). Their absence, if not a mere function of reduced stranding risk of orcas
366 and substantiated by future studies, may thus provide indirect evidence for the reduced
367 availability of seals prior to the Holocene and the sanctuary-like status of the incipient
368 Kattegat as a largely predator-free zone, or both.

369 Most currently dated Late Glacial whales from the circum-Kattegat fall into the
370 interstadial and especially the Allerød, while whale remains dating to the Younger Dryas
371 climatic recession are rare (**Fig. 9A**). This pattern is broadly consistent with expectations
372 based on the modern-day ecology of large baleen whales, especially bowheads, whose
373 distribution is strongly regulated by the presence and extension of sea ice (Insley et al.
374 2021; Citta et al. 2023). It is also notable that in today's Russian north, polar bears turn

375 to cetacean carcasses as a key nutritional resource only during warm phases (Laidre et al.
376 2018) and it is expected that, by extension, human whale-carcass availability would have
377 been a relevant strategy during interglacial/interstadial conditions. Conversely, this would
378 also be the period in which pinnipeds would be difficult to access, or completely absent
379 from the area because of the attendant contraction of sea ice in the circum-Kattegat.

380 A key question is therefore how common whale beaching was in the past and how
381 it can possibly be related to patterns in the archaeological record, especially during the
382 Allerød. Whale stranding risk is contingent on many different factors but rapid and
383 sustained climate change as well as storminess are key influences (Evans et al. 2005;
384 Mannino et al. 2015; Bradshaw, Evans, and Hindell 2006). Other important factors are
385 the bathymetry of the ocean and coastal topography (Brabyn and McLean 1992; Laidre
386 et al. 2018). Gradual land-sea transitions and shallow coastal water with extensive
387 intertidal zones, lagoons and fjords often act as natural whale traps and these features are
388 well-developed within the Skagerrak-Kattegat area and northern Jutland in particular (cf.
389 **Fig. 1**). This was likely further exaggerated by the highly dynamic shoreline
390 displacements at this time. In addition, comparing present-day and historical stranding
391 data from Denmark (Kinze 1995; Kinze, Thøstesen, and Olsen 2018) with the spatial
392 distribution of presently published Late Glacial whale remains (Aaris-Sørensen et al.
393 2010) reveals several possible beaching hotspots, one of which coincides with the west
394 coast of Vendsyssel (**Fig. 9B**). The prevalence of large bowhead whales within the eastern
395 extension of the Late Glacial North Atlantic ocean may be of particular relevance here,
396 as bowheads are known to float on the water surface even if they die in the open water
397 and are thus less likely to sink to the ground and disappear (Savelle, Dyke, and McCartney
398 2000), which increases both their visibility and recoverability – as ‘floating monuments’
399 – and the probability for wind or current-aided coastal deposition. Schmitt and colleagues

400 (2006) have suggested that westerly ocean currents were likely extremely powerful
401 during the Late Glacial and this would have further contributed to whale carcass accretion
402 on the west coast of northern Jutland, although tidal amplitudes were probably not
403 substantially elevated (Ward et al. 2016). In conjunction with the unique energetic value
404 of even a single adult bowhead body (equating c. 1300 seal carcasses: Laidre et al. 2018),
405 this may have provided an easily exploitable ecosystem service attracting people to the
406 north or, minimally, helping to sustain them in the otherwise challenging environments.

407 Compiling the currently available ^{14}C -dates of marine and terrestrial mammals
408 from Late Glacial northern Jutland qualifies this context (**Fig. 10; Supplementary**
409 **Information 1**). The dates suggest that 1) marine mammals including large baleen whales
410 arrived in and inhabited the area *before* Vendsyssel was colonised by terrestrial animals
411 such as reindeer, horse and bears, and that 2) the overlap between marine and terrestrial
412 animal occupation coincides with the Late Glacial interstadial, into which the bulk of the
413 archaeological evidence from Vendsyssel is also tentatively placed (Hellerøe et al. 2023;
414 Fischer 2012; Fischer, Clemmensen, et al. 2013). This may be taken as preliminary
415 evidence for an alluring adaptive context, with both terrestrial and marine resources
416 playing an important role for human foragers. Northern Jutland may have thus exerted a
417 ‘dual pull’ for Late Glacial foragers and the land-sea interface may have been crucial for
418 sustaining the earliest excursions into the area. It is conceivable that such land-sea
419 dynamics were anchored in patterns of seasonality, with the possibility of land and sea-
420 derived resources complementing each other, but this requires additional investigations.
421 Importantly, the overlap of dated terrestrial and marine mammals during the Late Glacial
422 interstadial confirms that Vendsyssel was in principle accessible on the land route, and
423 that Late Glacial human occupation in the European far North therefore does not require
424 boat-based explanations.

425 Against this larger context, the lithic techno-economic profile of the Hollendskær
426 sites can be critically re-assessed, and the large tanged point phenomenon possibly
427 acquires a new behavioural significance. What if large tanged points and their tanged
428 compatriots form an integral part of human adaptive systems which habitually integrated
429 coastal and coast-near freshwater resources and were characterised by high levels of
430 residential mobility? If Final Palaeolithic foragers were attracted by beached whales and
431 other northward migrating terrestrial mammals such as reindeer, these animals would
432 have been available only at particular times of the year and in particular locations and it
433 is reasonable to assume that humans would have attuned their landscape mobility
434 accordingly. In this scenario, foragers would have come to northern Vendsyssel for
435 particular reasons, and they would require technological solutions affording long-distance
436 movement and effective, flexible means to access and process the target animal resources.
437 The functional versatility of large tanged elements, paired with their durability and
438 significantly extended use-potential, makes them ideal for such long-distance
439 deployments. We may then perhaps more productively interpret them as multi-purpose
440 tools rather than as dedicated/specialised instances of hunting gear (see esp. Odell 1981).
441 Regarding diverse tanged elements as parts of an integrated *chaîne opératoire* of tool-use
442 strengthens this perspective considerably – they come into view as toolkit elements to be
443 carried around over considerable distances in order to be used in manifold ways. This
444 provides an alternative, organizational perspective (e.g., Shott 1986; Nelson 1991) on the
445 techno-typological make-up of higher latitude forager populations at the northern
446 extremes of Southern Scandinavia, linking the lithic record with the ecological specificity
447 of the region.
448

449 **Rethinking the role of the sea in Late Glacial forager adaptations**

450 Marine subsidising is an underappreciated dynamic within early forager adaptations in
451 north-western Europe and elsewhere. It is often assumed, especially with regard to Danish
452 prehistory, that the sea emerged as a key adaptive context of human behaviour only in the
453 course of the Holocene when dedicated ocean-oriented technologies evolved (Andersen
454 1970; 1996; Astrup 2018; Price 1985; Møhl 1970). Despite being widely acknowledged
455 as important contributors to human cultures worldwide (Demuth 2019; Lowenstein 1994;
456 Sakakibara 2020), whales, too, are conventionally regarded to become important only
457 with the emergence of whaling cultures, and this even though whales are prominently
458 depicted much earlier, for example in the rock art of Late Mesolithic Northern
459 Scandinavia (Clark 1947). Whales therefore clearly emerged as significant oceanic agents
460 in the context of human foragers societies and we suggest that some of these relationships
461 may have Late Glacial roots. Such early interactions between humans and whales are
462 important to investigate as they provide a much-needed deep-historical perspective on
463 forms of cohabitation and the co-evolutionary background of later human-whale relations
464 such as whaling.

465 Whales are cultural beings (e.g. Rendell and Whitehead 2001; Hersh et al. 2022;
466 Garland, Garrigue, and Noad 2022) and they were recognised as such presumably already
467 in the Pleistocene. Emerging evidence for the importance of cetaceans in human lifeways
468 during the Atlantic Magdalenian (e.g., Pétilion 2008; Álvarez-Fernández et al. 2014;
469 Lefebvre et al. 2021) and in some African Middle Stone Age contexts (Avery et al. 2008;
470 Dusseldorp and Langejans 2013; Kandel and Conard 2003; Mesfin et al. 2021; Steele and
471 Klein 2013) supports this view and offers the opportunity to rethink the role of the sea in
472 deep human prehistory. Whales, in particular, are notoriously ‘invisible’ in the
473 archaeological record (Smith and Kinahan 1984) but novel biomolecular methods, in

474 conjunction with robust theory-building, may open up new avenues to investigate land-
475 sea co-dependencies (Charpentier et al. 2022). To unravel relevant productivities and
476 salencies of the sea requires to reconsider multispecies systems, ecosystem relations and
477 other indirect lines of material evidence.

478 By mobilising archaeological evidence in such a manner and developing the
479 collaborative research programmes needed to tackle questions of human-sea relationships
480 in deep prehistory, archaeologists can draw on and contribute to the broader project of
481 the Blue Humanities, which seeks to map and interrogate the manifold entanglements of
482 humans and oceans that define part of the human experience and has shaped planetary
483 ecosystems (Mentz, Schaberg, and Bogost 2020; Mentz 2023; Buchanan 2018).
484 Archaeological perspectives and insights can in this way be crucial to safeguard oceanic
485 ecosystems in the present and to better understand human contributions to and
486 dependencies on maritime life across space and time, as well as changing human
487 sensibilities to watery affairs more generally.

488

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493

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495 The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

496

497 **Data availability statement**

498 All data reported in this paper are either already published elsewhere or are made
499 available with this paper.

500

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817 **Figures & captions**

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820 **Fig. 1.** Sea-level reconstruction and coastal topography of the circum-Kattegat area
 821 during the Late Glacial (after Houmark-Nielsen 2021). Red dots represent archaeological
 822 sites registered as Allerød (Lundström, Peters, and Riede 2021). Sites highlighted in
 823 orange belong to the Hollendskær find complex.

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827 **Fig. 2.** Tanged points and scrapers of probable Late Glacial provenience from the
 828 Hollendskær area published by Nilsson (1987). 1-3, 10, 12: tanged points from Ramsgård
 829 I; 4-6, 13-15: knives and tanged points from Ramsgård II; 7, 16-17: tanged point, tanged

830 scraper and tanged dihedral burin from Ramsgård VIII; 8-9: scraper and Wehlen-type
 831 scraper from Ramsgård I; 18-20: tanged points from Ramsgård V; 21-23: knives and
 832 tanged points from Varbro IV; 24-25: tanged point and tanged scraper from Ramsgård
 833 VI; 26: scraper from Ramsgård II; 27: tanged scraper from Ramsgård III; 28: tanged
 834 scraper from Varbro II; 29-30: scraper and tanged scraper from Ramsgård II; 31: tanged
 835 scraper from Ramsgård IX; 32: scraper from Ramsgård I. Relative scale.
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839 **Fig. 3.** Tanged points of probable Late Glacial provenience from Vendsyssel published
 840 by Nilsson (1987). 1-2: Vennebjerg; 3: Aastrup; 4, 12-13: Trudslev; 5: Aså-Melholt; 6:
 841 Nørre Lyngby; 7: Villerup; 8: Jerslev; 9: Vrensted; 10: Vrå; 11: Frydslund. Relative scale.
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844 **Fig. 4.** Map of the Hollendskær area with the major Late Glacial find concentrations
 845 discussed in this paper.

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Fig. 5. Selected stone tools from the new Hollendskær surface collection: 1-7 Ramsgård I; 8-12 Ramsgård II; 14, 16 Ramsgård IX; 15 Varbro V; 17-18 Ramsgård unspecified. Tanged points and knives: 1-2, 9, 12, 14; tanged scrapers: 3, 7-8, 15; endscrapers: 16-18; broken tangs: 4-6, 10-13.

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Fig. 6. Selected stone tools from the new Hollendskær surface collection: 1-6 Kærgård Syd; 7-11, 15-17 surface finds from the wider area; 12 Ramsgård II; 13-14 Kærgård Nord; 18 Ramsgård VII. Tanged points and knives: 1-4, 6, 8-9, 11, 13; tanged scrapers: 7, 18; enscrapers: 5, 14-16; broken tangs: 10, 17; broken curve-backed piece/Federmesser: 12.

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864 **Fig. 7.** Palaeogeographical reconstruction of the Zirfaea Sea (in blue) at its maximum
 865 extent during the early Allerød period, approx. 13,800 years ago. The dotted signature
 866 represents the extent of the subsequent Littorina transgression. Isobars indicate relative
 867 sea level (RSL) of the Yoldia, Zirfaea and Littorina transgressions (modified from Mertz,
 868 1924). Coastal zones denoted by “?” indicate areas where the original coastline could not
 869 be determined due to subsequent erosion. Zirfaea Beds have only been identified in the
 870 northern parts of Vendsyssel, and the depiction of the paleo-fjord in the Liver Å valley is
 871 inferred based on topographical considerations. The black triangles represent
 872 archaeological sites attributed to the Late Glacial period: 16: Smedegaarde, 40: Aastrup,
 873 42: Aså Melholt, 49: Frydslund, 53: Højvælde I, 54: Jerslev, 58: Nørre Lyngby, 66:
 874 Varbro, 67: Vennebjerg, 72: Em, 75: Vrensted, 76: Vrå, 80: Villerup, 100: Hollenskær
 875 sites, 138: Højvælde II, 172: Rubjerg, 185: Storemose.

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884 **Fig. 8.** Conceptual model comparing global eustatic sea-level (ESL) changes (Lambeck
 885 et al. 2014) with idealised curves representing steady isostatic lift (ISOL) in northern
 886 Vendsyssel (Hollendskær) and the Aalborg area, respectively (curves were created by an
 887 exponential fit to RSL). The corresponding relative sea-level (RSL) curves are plotted
 888 with the available data points of maximal RSL for the Yoldia, Zirfaea and Littorina
 889 transgressions (Mertz, 1924). Abbreviations: OD: Oldest Dryas, B-A: Bølling-Allerød
 890 Complex, YD: Younger Dryas, MWP-1A: melt water pulse 1A.

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895 **Fig. 9.** Geographic and chronological distribution of dated cetacean remains from the
 896 study area. A: Summed probability distributions of all dated whales and different key
 897 species (data from Aaris-Sørensen et al. 2010). Dates were calibrated in OxCal v.4.4.4
 898 using the Marine20 calibration curve (Heaton et al. 2020). The Younger Dryas is
 899 highlighted in dark purple. B: Map of whale remains from Denmark and Western Sweden
 900 dated to the Late Glacial (numbers correspond to IDs published in Aaris-Sørensen et al.
 901 2010: Table 2; cf. **Supplementary Information 1**). Modern and historical whale
 902 stranding hotspots are shaded in pink (based on dolphin, minke, sperm and fin whale data
 903 reported in Kinze 1995 and Kinze, Thøstesen, and Olsen 2018).

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906 **Fig. 10.** Modelled ¹⁴C-phase boundaries for dated marine and terrestrial mammals from
907 Northern Jutland (data from Aaris-Sørensen 2010 and Fischer et al. 2013; cf.
908 **Supplementary Information 2**). Figure was created in OxCal v.4.4.4 using the Marine20
909 calibration curve (Heaton et al. 2020). Green shading indicates the Late Glacial
910 Interstadial (Bølling-Allerød Complex).

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920 **Tables & captions**

921 **Tab. 1.** Lithic inventory of the Hollendskær sites as originally published by Nilsson
 922 (1987). Numbers with * in parentheses represent corrected counts.

	Varbro I	Varbro II	Varbro III	Varbro IV	Ramsgård I	Ramsgård II	Ramsgård III	Ramsgård IV	Ramsgård V	Ramsgård VI	Ramsgård VII	Ramsgård VIII	Ramsgård IX
<i>Total Tanged point</i>	3	1	1	3	10 (9*)	9 (7*)	1	1 (0*)	4	1	1	1	1
Complete Tanged point	1		1	3	5	4			3		1		
Incomplete Tanged point	2	1			5 (4*)	5 (3*)	1	1 (0*)	1	1		1	1
<i>Total scrapers</i>	2	2	4	1	6	7	3	5	3	2		2	2
Scrapers on flake	1	1	4		5 (3*)	5	3 (2*)	4	3	1		1	1
Scrapers on blade				1		1	1 (1*)	1					
Tanged scrapers (Wehlen)	1	1			1 (3*)	1				1		1	1
<i>Total Laterally Modified Laminar Pieces (LMP)</i>		1		1					1 (0*)				
<i>Total burins</i>	1		1		5	4	1	3	3			1	
Burin on flake			1		4	4	1	3	3				
Burin on blade					1								

Burin on tanged point	1											1	
Total borers								2	1				
Borer on flake								1	1				
Borer on blade								1					
Plain débitage and other worked/used blanks	31	28	27	23	53	94	34	38	23	4	2	3	3

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Tab. 2. Detailed breakdown of newly studied lithic assemblages from the Hollendskær area.

Site	Nørre Ramsgård	Ramsgård I	Ramsgård II	Ramsgård IV	Ramsgård V	Ramsgård VI	Ramsgård VII	Ramsgård IX	loose finds Tommy	loose finds Tommy	Varbro V	Kaergård Nord	loose finds (small box)	loose finds (large box)	Kaergård Syd (Box 1)	Kaergård Syd (Box 2)	Kaergård Syd (Box 3)	Kaergård Syd (Box 4)	Kaergård Syd	Loose finds (merged)	
Total débitage (unretouched flakes)	46	12	13	2 2				2	11	16	12	27		12 8		8	68	15		91	12 9
Total flakes	20	3	4	8					2	10	4	10		46		3	33	5		41	46
Complete flakes	17	3	1	6					1	8	2	9		24		2	28	4		34	24
Total blades	19	8	8	9				1	8	1	7	5		54			13	7		20	55
Complete blades	8	2	4	4					6	1	3	5		30			3	3		6	30
Total bladesets	4		1	4				1		1		5		20			7	2		9	20
Complete bladesets								1		1		1		11			5			5	11
CTE (core)	1	1							1					2		4				4	2

<i>trimming elements)</i>																						
<i>Burin spall & co.</i>										2												
<i>Micro burin leftover</i>										1?												
Total Fragments	2			1					4		5		6		1	15	1		17	6		
<i>Pieces with Cortex</i>	23	7	11	15					6	5	8	8	1	36		9	40	12		61	37	
Total cores	2	1	2					1			3	2		2			2?	1		3?	2	
<i>Flake cores</i>		1						1				1										
<i>Blade cores</i>			2															1		1		
<i>Bladet cores</i>	2										3	1		2				2?		2?	2	
Total scrapers	4	6	6	10	2			3	2			3	2	3	6	1		3	3		7	9
<i>Scrapers on flake complete</i>	1	0	2	1				1	1			1		2	1				1		1	3
<i>Scrapers on flake incomplete</i>	2			1?				1							3							3
<i>Scrapers on blade complete</i>			3	1	1			1				1	1			1		1	1		3	
<i>Scrapers on blade incomplete</i>		3		3											2			2	1		3	2
<i>Tanged scrapers (Wehlein)</i>	1	3	1	4	1			1				1		1								1

<i>Total number of tools</i>	12	17	28	22	5	1	3	4	0	2	8	6	8	23	9	2	6	4		18	30
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